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WHY TEACHERS SHOULD PREPARE A LESSON PLAN?

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***Abstract:** This article examines why teachers should prepare a lesson plan for every lesson they conduct and shows different types of lesson plans, also ways to effective lesson conducting.*

***Key words:** Interactive and evaluative decisions, purpose of the lesson, internal and external reasons, daily lesson planning.*

Introduction

New era of modern education requires new and effective ways of teaching. When it comes to teaching English language, any teacher of English can not get by lesson planning. So what is lesson planning? Lesson plan is a teacher's detailed description of the course of instruction for an individual lesson. Additionally, in pedagogical resources, lesson plan is described as a list of objectives, these may be stated as behavioral objectives - what the student is expected to be able to do upon completion of the lesson, or as knowledge objectives - what the student is expected to know upon completion of the lesson.

Most teachers prefer yearly, term, unit, weekly, and daily lesson planning. As it describes itself, yearly and term lesson plans are made for specific period: for a month, term or for two years etc. On the other hand, a unit plan is a little bit dissimilar. A unit plan is a list of lessons related to one specific topic. For instance lessons about weather,

which includes several lessons including vocabulary, grammar and language skills developed during the process.

Even if these types of lesson plans are crucial in conducting a lesson, daily planning is the most dominant one. The major reason for that, daily lesson planning is the end result of a compound planning process that includes the yearly, term, and unit plans that were mentioned above.

Main part

One of the aspects that reveals the importance of daily planning – interactive and evaluative decisions of teachers. Interactive decision is a framework in which all the detailed and specific parts of the lesson is made, when teachers exactly know what to do during and after the lesson. Moreover, an evaluative decision is kind of a judgment which includes selecting appropriate information for a task, determining the strength of an argument, formulating a research question, drawing conclusions from evidence. Also this is connected with critical thinking of the teacher, how teacher can critically examine the process of the lesson in a subjective way. These two decisions are prime aspects of daily planning.

On the other hand these two types of decisions should be appropriate for the purpose of the lesson. There is no one description for the purpose of the lesson, because it depends on what teacher is going to teach and what teacher expects from their learners. It can be different objectives. For instance, if one's topic of the lesson is "Using advanced vocabulary in writing", obviously the lesson includes learning new vocabulary and being fluent in using them. In that case, the purpose of the lesson would be: students should be able to use advanced vocabulary and use them appropriately in numerous writing cases.

Moreover, teachers do daily planning for internal reasons – to feel themselves more confident, because they already know what to teach and how to teach, which of course enables the process to run smoothly and prevent the unexpected changes before they actually occur. A striking example, when a student asks something that teachers don't know or forget.

On the other hand, daily planning is done because of the external reasons too. As it was mentioned above, yearly or term lesson plans are often prepared in schools, universities etc., where the main purpose is to meet the expectations that are shown in several objectives. This might be very different from the internal reasons for the daily planning. Because, if internal reason is important for one teacher – for him/her only, the external reason is not only important but required with a deadline from the supervisor, administration and etc. So that is why every lesson should be planned and prepared for any unexpected situation.

Conclusion

The importance of daily planning is obvious now, but people should not forget that teachers can never be “over ready”. Most people think that teachers are source of information and unlimited rate of questions. But teachers are also people who teach their students a new knowledge that they don't know, being prepared and ready for every lesson depends on a level of responsibility and dedication for their work.

As in every successful result the process with small steps plays a huge role, in a successful lesson too, daily plans, daily evaluation and daily analysis also takes a key role. Also, daily planning is a log of what has been taught to students. Because of the fact that lesson plan includes tasks, exercises that are given for the students, teachers will precisely know the progress of the students. Often a lesson plan is outlined as a translation of the curriculum into clear daily goals for student learning that include a description of the objective and a way to measure the student's attainment of it. A few standard measurement methods are tests, homework and assignments. So if teachers plan daily their lessons, it is easier for them to examine and check the effectiveness of the lessons they conduct.

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